

A Self-Stabilizing Method for Dynamically Redundant Autonomously Distributed Real-Time Video

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Abstract: This document is a **Technical Note** that reports on the design and proof-of-concept of a self-distributed Selective Forwarding Unit (SFU) architecture for real-time video streaming. Unlike a full research article, this note emphasizes the **practical motivation, implementation details, and observed behaviors** of the system. The central idea is to address the limitations of traditional prediction-based scaling by introducing a **finite state machine (FSM)-based self-stabilizing method** that enables autonomous scale-out and scale-in of distributed SFUs under dynamic traffic conditions.

Fig. 1: Cooperative autonomously distributed topology

Keywords: WebRTC, SFU, autonomous distributed topology, FSM, HALT metric, real-time streaming, scalability

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Scaling SFU-based real-time video streaming is challenging due to unpredictable and sudden spikes in user demand. Conventional centralized scaling approaches often depend on traffic prediction and controller-driven resource allocation, which fail to react quickly enough during extreme fluctuations.

1.2 Gap

Prediction-based scaling cannot handle **instantaneous traffic surges**, leading to bottlenecks, instability, and degraded user experience.

1.3 Scope

This Technical Note introduces a **self-distributed FSM-based SFU architecture** that autonomously handles replication and redundancy. It outlines the **design principles, FSM protocols, and practical implementation details**, with observations from proof-of-concept testing.

2. Design and Method

2.1 Self-Distributed Topology

The architecture eliminates central bottlenecks by enabling each SFU node to participate in an **autonomous distribution topology**. Nodes coordinate locally rather than relying on a centralized orchestrator.

As shown in Figure 1, the topology organizes nodes into a decentralized structure where replication flows outward from load

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hotspots, ensuring redundancy without centralized coordination.

2.2 FSM-Based Protocols

Fig. 2: Scale-Out Protocol

Scaling decisions are governed by a **finite state machine (FSM)** embedded within each node. FSM transitions define how nodes replicate under load and withdraw when demand decreases.

Figure 2, 3 depicts the FSM transition model used for autonomous scale-out and scale-in.

Fig. 3: Scale-In Protocol

2.3 HALT Metric

The **HALT metric** is introduced to estimate node capacity and trigger FSM transitions. HALT combines latency and throughput into a simple heuristic for load estimation.

3. Implementation

3.1 Frameworks and Environment

The proof-of-concept implementation was built using

- **libdatachannel** for WebRTC signaling and media transport.
*1

*1 <https://github.com/paullouisageneau/libdatachannel>

- **MySQL BlackHole engine** for lightweight statistics handling.
- **MySQL Client Compatible** trilogy.*2
- **Google Cloud Platform (GCP)** for deployment and distributed testing. Signaling(*3)

3.2 Replication and Statistics Reporting

Each node performs lightweight replication and periodically exchanges minimal statistics with peers. This minimizes coordination overhead and avoids central bottlenecks.

Figure 4 shows the replication flow and peer-to-peer exchange of statistics.

Fig. 4: Neighbor-closed topology

4. Evaluation / Observations

4.1 RTT Measurements

Table 1 presents round-trip time (RTT) measurements, demonstrating the effects of different edge node placements.

Table 1: measured RTT Tokyo - Region

EnterPrise LAN Tokyo-Tokyo	4.3 ms
EnterPrise LAN Tokyo-Mumbai	135.2 ms
EnterPrise Wifi Tokyo-Tokyo	7.8 ms
EnterPrise Wifi Tokyo-Mumbai	138.5 ms
Mobile Docomo Tokyo-Tokyo	43.0 ms
Mobile Softbank Tokyo-Tokyo	43.0 ms
Mobile Softbank Tokyo-Mumbai	180.7 ms
Mobile AU Tokyo-Tokyo	43.0 ms
Mobile AU Tokyo-Mumbai	176.2 ms

4.2 Effects of Edge Placement(Origin, Proxy)

Figure 5 shows the observed impact of edge node distribution on latency and stability. Placement closer to clients reduced RTT variance and improved resilience.

*2 <https://github.com/trilogy-libraries/trilogy>

*3 <https://cloud.google.com/functions?hl=ja>

Fig. 5: Inter-Region RTT

4.3 Scope of Results

The evaluation presented in this Technical Note is limited to **proof-of-concept observations** rather than a full-scale statistical study. Specifically:

- **Round-trip time (RTT) measurements** were conducted in a limited set of deployment scenarios and summarized in Table 1.
- **Effects of edge placement** were observed in small-scale experiments, as illustrated in Figure 5
- The focus is on **highlighting qualitative behaviors** such as reduced RTT variance and improved stability when edge nodes are closer to clients.

A large-scale evaluation of **Quality of Experience (QoE)** across diverse network conditions and extended time frames has not yet been performed. Future work is required to validate these findings under production-scale workloads.

5. Discussion

5.1 Practical Implications

- **Elimination of central bottlenecks** by relying on self-distributed coordination.
- **Lightweight statistics exchange** to keep overhead minimal.
- **Resilient operation** under unpredictable and dynamic traffic surges.

5.2 Limitations

- Large-scale **Quality of Experience (QoE) evaluation** remains untested.
- Additional research is required to confirm stability at production scale.

5.3 Distributed vs. Autonomously Distributed

“Distributed” ≠ “Autonomously Distributed.”

Fig. 6: Self Distributed

- Distributed systems may still rely on controllers, coordinators, or managers.
- This creates bottlenecks:
 - Oversized statistics collection systems
 - High reporting costs

Our design eliminates central roles and achieves true self-stabilization.

6. Conclusion

This technical note introduced a self-stabilizing approach for dynamically redundant, autonomously distributed SFU clusters. By employing FSM-based cooperation and HALT-driven scaling decisions, the system avoids centralized bottlenecks and maintains fault tolerance through primary and redundant paths. A lightweight statistics design reduces cache interference and reporting overhead, enabling SFUs to focus on packet processing.

Our proof-of-concept deployments and RTT measurements highlight the importance of edge placement and distributed decision-making in practical cloud environments. In addition, the proposed architecture exhibits key self- properties* [13]:

6.1 Self-* Properties

- **Self-configuration:** Edge-SFUs autonomously replicate and join clusters.
- **Self-organization:** routing and topology adapt dynamically to load and failures.
- **Self-healing:** nodes recover from crashes with seamless failover, Fig.15
- **Self-management/optimization:** HALT-driven adaptive policies (e.g., DSCP prioritization) sustain efficiency.

The contribution of this note is to provide architectural insights and implementation guidelines, rather than a full-scale evaluation, to support further development of scalable, cloud-native real-time video delivery.

7. Latency and Connection Stability

High RTTs (100–200 ms) between clients and distant Edge-SFUs cause ICE/STUN/TURN failures. Measured RTTs in Table.1 show severe degradation under mobile networks. To mitigate this, ICE timeouts must be tuned (e.g., `iceGatheringTimeout`, `iceConnectionTimeout`).

8. Related Work

Fig. 7: Semi-Intensive Conventional Monitoring

Table 2: Related Work

Gossip [1] Quorum Consensus Fig.6	Reduces monitoring cost, but only at the observation layer, not at control.
ENTS [2] (Edge Task Scheduling) Fig.7, Table.3	Similar use case (video analytics) but focuses on centralized scheduling, not streaming.
DMSA [3] Decentralized Micro-services Table.4	Decentralizes monitoring but retains centralized discovery queries.
P2P [12] Unstructured/Structured Fig.10, Fig.11	Introduces hierarchical overlays with super-peers, which reintroduce centralization
Kademlia-based WebRTC, [6] Fig.8, Table.5	Efficient DHT, but requires global structure and is redundant for cloud-native environments (regions/zones already managed).
SDN-based Scalable conferencing, [5]	Offloads SFU logic into P4 switches, skipping encryption/decryption, unsuitable for cloud cost-optimization
Enel Graph Propagation Scaling [7]	Uses graph propagation with coordinators; unlike our fully autonomous FSM-based approach.
US20210218681A1 Flash Crowd Management In Real-Time Streaming [11] Table.6	Central servers predict and handle spikes, scaling at the cluster level. In contrast, our method uses HALT-driven autonomous Edge replication.
AWS Chime Media Pipelines [9]	high abstraction and developer ease, but fully centralized, consuming extensive cloud resources.
Jitsi Conference Focus [10]	similarly centralized, constrained by heavy backend control.

Table 3: ENTS , This Architecture

Item	ENTS	This Proposal
Use Case	Video Analysis : Data Stream Task	Video Delivery : WebRTC
Scheduling	Online Algorithm + Global Optimization	Scale-in/Scale-out via Local Decisions

Table 4: DMSA vs This Architecture

Item	DMSA	This Proposal
Decentralization Depth	Depends on central list, API router nature	No central list needed, self-forming topology
Limit, Risk	Bottlenecks in reflecting changes to overall definition, redefinition of centralization	Minimal scale-in/out load

Table 5: Kademlia , FSM/GCP

Item	Kademlia	This Proposal
Overview	Node search using XOR distance between node IDs	Selects optimal node using only local custom metrics per region/zone VM
Placement	Irregular and skewed node placement	Nodes structured logically and physically by region, zone, etc.
Search	$O(\log n)$ based on XOR distance	Real-time determination from RTT and HALT values of neighboring nodes
FSM	DHT distributed management	Nodes/devices manage only neighbor statistics
Failure	DHT redundancy	Nodes/devices manage only nearby statistics
Delay	k-bucket maintenance, DHT refresh	Node-specific local metric updates
Adaptability	Unspecified number of P2P nodes	GCP / Cloud, etc. Simple mechanism adapted to structured infrastructure

Table 6: IS20210218681A1 vs This Architecture

Item	US20210218681A1	This Proposal
Traffic Spike Prediction	Centralized, Central Server + Management System	Strongly Autonomous Distributed: Each Node Independently Decides, Acts
Scaling Granularity	Scale-out at cluster level	Self-replication at local/neighbor Edge level

Fig. 8: Kademlia XOR Metric

Fig. 9: Cloud Native Edge-SFU Selection

Fig. 10: Unstructured Structured 2-Layer Topology

Fig. 11: Super Peer Network

Listing 1: Naming system

```
{region}-{module-type}-{uuid}-{suffix}

# module-type = origin, edge, connector
# suffix = user-hash
```

Shows naming and query systems used to select Edge-SFUs dynamically with HALT-based filtering.

9. Implementation

Fig. 12: Other Region

Fig. 13: Multi Region

Fig. 14: Optimization and Reconfiguration of Communication Paths Based on Local Judgment

Fig. 15: Auto Failover based on local determination

10. Appendix

10.1 Code Listings

Listing 2: Neighbor Edge Node Selection Algorithm

```
def neighbor_edge(client_location, edge_stats):
    candidate_edges = []
    for edge in edge_stats:
        if is_in_region(edge.location, client_location):
            halt_per_session = edge.halt_value / edge.
            session_count
            rt = estimate_rtt(client_location, edge.
            location)
            candidate_edges.append((edge,
            halt_per_session, rt))

    if not candidate_edges:
        new_edge = create_edge_instance_neighbor(
        client_location)
        parent_edge = find_neighbor_existing_edge(
        client_location)
        connect_edges_via_connector(parent_edge,
        new_edge)
        return new_edge

    candidate_edges.sort(key=lambda x: (-x[1], x[2]))
    return candidate_edges[0][0]
```

Listing 3: Statistics Report

```
INSERT INTO stats
('session_id', 'event', 'option', 'created_at')
VALUES
({session_id}, {event}, {option}, {created_at}),
({session_id}, {event}, {option}, {created_at}),
... ( x BULK SIZE )
({session_id}, {event}, {option}, {created_at}),
;
```

Listing 4: CPU-Core-Mask

```
cpu_set_t cpumask;
CPU_ZERO(&cpumask);
CPU_SET(cpuid, &cpumask);
//
if (cpuid >= 0){
    if (pthread_setaffinity_np(pthread_self(), sizeof(
    cpumask), &cpumask) != 0) {
        PANIC("Unable to set affinity: %s", strerror(errno
    ));
        return(ERR);
    }
    return(OK);
}
```

Listing 5: Sample RTT measurement

```
peer_connection = new RTCPeerConnection({iceServers: [],
iceTransportPolicy: 'all'});
peer_connection.onicegatheringstatechange = (state) => {
    if (peer_connection.iceGatheringState === 'complete')
    {
        const ans = peer_connection.localDescription;
        answer({"type": ans.type, sdp: ans.sdp, link: ''})
    }
};
peer_connection.ondatachannel = (event) => {
    data_channel = event.channel;
    data_channel.onopen = () => {
        data_channel.send(JSON.stringify({"t0": nowJST()}))
    };
    data_channel.onmessage = (event) => {
        var jsn = JSON.parse(event.data);
        if ('t5' in jsn) {
            jsn['t6'] = nowJST();
            topology.value = JSON.stringify(jsn, null, 2);
        } else if ('t3' in jsn) {
            jsn['t4'] = nowJST();
            data_channel.send(JSON.stringify(jsn));
        } else if ('t1' in jsn) {
            jsn['t2'] = nowJST();
            data_channel.send(JSON.stringify(jsn));
        }
    };
};
peer_connection.setRemoteDescription(offer_json);
peer_connection.createAnswer().then(answer => {
    peer_connection.setLocalDescription(answer);
});
```

10.2 Cache Pollution Avoidance

Edge-SFUs must prioritize packet forwarding over auxiliary tasks. Statistics collection, logging, or control messages can cause cache pollution and degrade forwarding throughput. Our implementation isolates forwarding-critical threads from reporting tasks, ensuring cache locality is preserved for real-time processing.

Fig. 16: Parallel Processin on Many-Core CPUs

10.3 Origin-Edge Connectivity

- Origin-SFUs and Edge-SFUs connect through NAT traversal connector modules.
- Clients search for nearby Edge-SFUs; if none exist, a new Edge-SFU (B) is spawned near the client.

- The new Edge-SFU automatically connects to an existing Edge-SFU (A) and integrates into the topology.

Fig. 17: Origin Edge Connectivity

10.4 Improving Accuracy of Statistics – HALT Value

Traditional metrics (session count, CPU usage, bandwidth) fail to measure actual spare capacity.

- We introduce HALT (Hardware Available Load Threshold) as a real metric.
- HALT measures residual processing capacity after each loop, incorporating CPU idle, I/O waits, throughput, etc.
- This enables more reliable distributed decision-making

10.5 Oversized Statistics Systems

Traditional systems often suffer from bloated statistics pipelines (HTTP APIs, external analytics). These consume CPU, memory, and network resources, ironically destabilizing the system. Our approach keeps statistics simple (local MySQL + replication), enabling SFUs to focus on packet processing.

10.6 Handover

ICE/TURN negotiation introduces latency, Buffers synchronize 2–30 frames between source and target Edge-SFUs

Table 7: Handover Entities

Item	Overview
Mobile Device	UE(User Equipment)
HandOver Origin	Currently Connected Edge-SFU
HandOver Dest	Target Edge-SFU
Connector	Stream-Connector during handover
Buffer	Media(video) buffering during handover

Fig. 18: Handover Sequence

11. Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

12. Author Contributions

Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing-Original Draft, Writing-Review and Editing, Visualization, Supervision, Project administration: D.Sugisawa.

13. AI Disclosure

The author used a large language model ChatGPT, OpenAI to assist in proofreading, grammar checking, and improving the clarity of expressions. The author reviewed and is responsible for the final content.

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References

- [1] SHASHIKANT ILAGER. A Decentralized and Self-Adaptive Approach for Monitoring Volatile Edge Environments. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2405.07806v1>
- [2] Mingjin Zhang. ENTS: An Edge-native Task Scheduling System for Collaborative Edge Computing. <http://arxiv.org/abs/2210.07842v1>
- [3] Yuang Chen. DMSA: A Decentralized Microservice Architecture for Edge Networks. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2501.00883v1>
- [4] Chmieliauskas. Evaluation of Uplink Video Streaming QoE in 4G and 5G Cellular Networks Using Real-World Measurements. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3554340>
- [5] Oliver Michel. Scalable Video Conferencing Using SDN Principles. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2503.11649>
- [6] Ryle Zhou. Decentralized WebRTC P2P Network Using Kademlia. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2206.07685>
- [7] Dominik Scheinert. Enel:Context-Aware Dynamic Scaling of Distributed Dataflow Jobs using Graph Propagation. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2108.12211>
- [8] Shaher Daoud and Yanzen Qu. A COMPREHENSIVE STUDY OF DSCP MARKINGS' IMPACT ON VOIP QOS IN HFC NETWORKS. <https://airconline.com/ijenc/V11N5/11519cnc01.pdf>
- [9] AWS Chime Media Pipelines. <https://docs.aws.amazon.com/chime-sdk/latest/dg/media-pipelines.html>
- [10] jitsi. Jitsi Conference Focus. <https://github.com/jitsi/jicofo>

- [11] US20210218681A1. Flash crowd management in real-time streaming.
<https://patents.google.com/patent/US20210218681A1/en>
- [12] Tao GU. A Hierarchical Semantic Overlay for P2P Search.
<https://arxiv.org/pdf/2003.05001>
- [13] Babaoglu. Self-star Properties in Complex Information Systems : Conceptual and Practical Foundations.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/b136551>